

Involvement of Predictors of Achievements Contributing to Sports of Female Student Athletes of Secondary Schools of Pakistan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 11, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: November 11, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Social Support, Cultural, Personal, Interferential Factors, Sports Contribution</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5678752</p>	<p><i>The aim of the current research was to determine the involvement of predictors of achievement in sports contribution of female student athletes along with moderating construct. Predictors of achievement such as social support factors, social cultural factors, and social personal factors with social interferential factors involved greatly in sports contribution of female athletes at school level. The quantitative research approach to fill the questionnaires from 590 samples was applied randomly. The subjects have belonged to the school education department overall Pakistan. The information was gathered from three provinces (Punjab, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, and Sindh) of Pakistan. Data was collected from 9th and 10th grade school athletes. Afterwards, survey data was analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation coefficients, and path analysis with Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). The findings of path analysis revealed that being a moderator (social interferential factor) contributed significantly to the outcome variable in hypothesized model. The findings concluded that support from siblings and peers should be keenly provided and management of the institutions (school) should be responsible to make sure the availability of sports facilities for female students. The associations of female sports should step forward to form the practice environment in Pakistan at present. The current study found that the social interferential factor was fully moderated the relationship in conjunction with social support, social cultural, social personal individually, and the female athletes' sports contribution. Positive relationships were revealed between all constructs and the sports' contribution of female athletes. The female sports organizations and associations are needed to raise the issue to higher authorities on this gender disparity and demand for equal rights of sports opportunities for females.</i></p>

Introduction

There is an optimistic association between performance in sports and stages of academic success. [Al-Qattan \(2005\)](#) expresses that academic performance may be raised and enhanced through engaging in sports activities. By engaging in sports events, school girls may be needed to keep up respectable marks to encounter suitability to participate in sports or primary happiness ([Wilson, 2009](#)). Moreover, contribution in planned sports activities encourages not only academic success but also individual and social improvement. Muslim females in Pakistan are withdrawn by their parents, family members, and the general public from their participating in sports events ([Khan, Jamil, Khan, Kareem, & Imran, 2012](#)). Based on the practical pieces of evidence, it is likely to suppose the contribution of the sports of female athletes may be significantly associated with the social support factor. The contribution and training of schoolgirls in numerous sports events touched the social performance individually in today's era ([Al-Qattan, 2005](#)).

Sports contribution is a central issue in sport workout devotion and youngsters' enduring exercise. Alternatively, parents have a social impact that is upsetting youngsters overall ([Giannitsopoulou, Kosmidou, & Zisi, 2010](#)). If parents are interested to involve their teenagers in sports training from the very beginning of their age and development to extend their complete potential, at that moment it is absolutely important to need a respectable atmosphere through these developmental ages and parents perform an extremely significant part in this development ([Marcen, Gimeno, Gomez, Saenz, & Gutierrez, 2013](#)). [Cremades, Donlon, and Poczwardowski \(2013\)](#) categorized into three types of parental involvement in female athletes' carrier. First, under-involved, measured destructive, denotes a comparative deficiency of expressive, monetary, or purposeful asset on the parental behalf. Secondly, the moderate-involved family, parents are helpful, but final choices concerning participation and levels of accomplishment are completed by the athletes themselves. Last, in the over-involved parental range, also measured destructive, parents have an extreme extent of involvement in their

youngsters' sporty achievement. School athletes interconnect with peers, the effort for the highest concern of the team, and pick up to keep an eye on guidelines of the team head (Wilson, 2009). Accordingly, social support is not supposed to contribute to the female athletes' sports contribution through influencing social interference. Parents have an indispensable effect on children's sports contribution (Miguel, Leo, Oliva, Amado, & Calvo, 2013). Parents and siblings, particularly of similar sex, must have an important effect on a child's overview and continued physical and sport movement (Willson, 2007).

Body shape gratification in the public may also evaluate, for instance, how female athletes observe their existing body shape concerning what they would want to appear physically (Gittelsohn, Harris, Thorne-Lyman, Hanley, Barnie, & Zinman, 1996). Similarly, athletes invest their maximum time struggling to enhance and improve technical and developmental expertise, while considerable exertion may be invested in struggling to increase or upgrade features of fitness (Williams & Hodges, 2005). The aptitude of the sports teacher plans a practice environment that raises optimum learning, therefore, develops maximum considerable sources to female athlete growth (Baker, Horton, Robertson-Wilson, & Wall, 2003). Coaches perform an important part in heightening an athlete's training phase and maybe devising total control over the practice settings (Davids & Baker, 2007).

Contesting the domination of the gender structure can be approached by enhancing female contribution in sports that can secure the social prominence of females' physical appearance (Crissey & Honea, 2006). Furthermore, contribution in sport decreases devotion to leading social beauty principles, encourages optimistic body appearance, and discourages tangled eating disorders. So, it is likely to suppose the contribution of the sports of female athletes may be significantly associated with social personal factors.

Socio-economic position restricts the opportunity of particular student athletes being able to participate as particular best athletes have private schoolings, appear summer sports training camps or participate in club sports yearly (Wilson, 2009). Sports facilities for single and team sport do not continuously appreciate the requirement for uncertain uniforms (Qureshi & Ghouri, 2011). Sports females and athletes are constantly overlooked by the sports media means the media is offering the appearance that females have not the same worth equated to male sports and male athletes (Trolan, 2013). Thus, social culture may extremely not significantly contribute the female athletes' sports contribution through influencing social interference.

Hypotheses of the Research

The following hypotheses were formulated for the existing study:

- i. There is a significant association between predictors of achievement (social support factors, social cultural factors, social personal factors, and social interferential factors) and the contribution of the sports of female student athletes.
- ii. There is a significant contribution of predictors of achievement (social support factors, social cultural factors, social personal factors) in the outcome variable (sports contribution) in conjunction with moderating construct (social interferential factors) through path analysis.

Methodological Procedures

Participants

The subjects have belonged to the school education department overall Pakistan. The information was gathered from three provinces (Punjab, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, and Sindh) of Pakistan.

Population and Samples

Population refers to the whole gathering of individuals, proceedings, or possessions of curiosity particular the researcher desires to examine (Sekaran, 2003). The population (N-13674) with samples (n-590) of the study consisted of various sports disciplines (games). All active female athletes studying in 9th and 10th grades of secondary schools overall Pakistan who remained with the medal in one sport event were considered the population of the existing research.

Instrument and Data Collection

Survey Questionnaire is mostly brought into being with a broad idea of the respondent. The current survey questions have consisted of two types: demographic and content questions. Demographic items pursue expressive data about the participants, such as age, participated sport, experience, contribution level, or institution name (Graziano & Raulin, 2013). Whereas, content questions are considered the most important questions with Likert scale on a survey questionnaire that inquired about the participants' views, approaches, information, and conduct. The 590 survey questionnaires were distributed among female student athletes of 9th and 10th grade school education and 313 female athletes gave their feedback to the researchers in form of filled questionnaires.

Data Analysis Methods

The obtained survey data was edited into SPSS v-26 for further process. The approaches used for statistical purposes were descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and path analysis through AMOS and Structural Equation Modeling (SEM).

Results

The results of the descriptive statistics about the age, playing experience, and sports contribution level of 313 respondents in Table 1.

The age level of the female student players was considered between 14 years to 16 years. The mean age of the participants was found 15.42 and the standard deviation was calculated .981. School females hold playing experiences between 1 to 4 years during their academic careers displayed in Table 1. The mean value of playing experiences of athletes was 2.26 years, whereas, they had .901 as standard deviation. Student females played within their five levels of sports contribution from inter-school to all Pakistan inter-board competitions (Table 1).

All sub-variables of social support factors were positively low and high correlated ($r = .17$ to $.74$) and significant among each other in Table 2. Furthermore, all sub-variables of social support factors were positively low, moderate, and high correlated significantly with the all sub-variables of social cultural factor between $r = .13$ to $.70$ however, two sub-variables found non-significant (socio-economic status and sports facilities with peers).

Table 1

Respondents' distribution by age, playing experience, contribution level (n-313)

Construct	14 years		15 years		16 years		17 years		Mean	SD
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
Age	61	19.5	111	35.5	90	28.7	51	16.3	15.42	.981
Playing Experience	1 year		2 years		3 years		4 years		2.26	.901
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
	76	24.3	102	32.6	114	36.4	21	6.7		
Sport Contribution Level	All Pakistan Inter-Board		Provincial Inter-Board		Inter-District		Inter-Tehsil		Inter-School	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
	56	17.9	96	30.7	72	23.0	48	15.3	41	13.1

Note: F: Frequency;

%: Percentage

Moreover, all sub-variables of social support factor were positively low, moderate, and high correlated significantly with all sub-variables of social personal factors between $r = .14$ to $.79$ except between peers and body image that was found non-significant. On the other hand, all sub-variables of social support factors were negatively low and high correlated with all sub-variables of social interferential factors between $r = -.16$ to $-.75$, and all were found significant.

All sub-variables of social cultural factors were positively low to high correlated significantly ($r = .37$ to $.68$) among each other. Moreover, all sub-variables of social cultural factors were positively low, moderate, and high correlated significantly with all sub-variables of social personal factors between $r = .25$ to $.69$. On the other hand, all sub-variables of social cultural factors were negatively moderate to high correlated significantly with all sub-variables of social interferential factors between $r = -.35$ to $-.77$ in Table 2.

The two sub-variables of social personal factors were positive, strong, and significant correlation ($r = .61$) among each other in Table 2. On the other hand, all sub-variables of social personal factors were negatively moderate to high correlated significantly with all sub-variables of social interferential factors between $r = -.43$ to $-.68$. However, the two sub-variables of social interferential factors were positive, strong, and significant correlations ($r = .70$) among each other. All sub-variables of sports contribution of female athletes were positively and significantly correlated (low to high) with all social support factors ($r = .15$ to $.85$). Moreover, all sub-variables of sports contribution of female athletes were positively low, moderate, and high correlated significantly with all social cultural factors between $r = .35$ to $.84$. Therefore, all sub-variables of sports contribution of female athletes were positively moderate and high correlated significantly with all social personal factors between $r = .47$ to $.75$. On the other hand, all sub-variables of sports contribution of female athletes were negatively and significantly correlated (moderate to high) with all social interferential factors between $r = -.71$ to $-.78$ (Table 2).

Table 2*Inter-correlations among constructs (n=313)*

Constructs with Sub-Constructs		Parents	Siblings	Peers	Sport Teachers	Socio-Economic Status	Sports Facilities	Rewards for Achievements	Sport Media	Body Image	Practice Environment	Dress Code	Gender Inequality	Health	Personal Interest Drive
Social Support Factor															
Parents	Pearson Correlation	–													
Siblings	Pearson Correlation	.325**	–												
Peers	Pearson Correlation	.189**	.278**	–											
Sport Teachers	Pearson Correlation	.743**	.346**	.165**	–										
Social Cultural Factor															
Socio-Economic Status	Pearson Correlation	.401**	.153**	.050	.362**	–									
Sport Facilities	Pearson Correlation	.603**	.223**	.101	.504**	.404**	–								
Rewards for Achievements	Pearson Correlation	.795**	.295**	.157**	.700**	.419**	.527**	–							
Sport Media	Pearson Correlation	.351**	.130*	.139*	.286**	.677**	.418**	.366**	–						
Social Personal Factor															
Body Image	Pearson Correlation	.516**	.223**	.063	.470**	.263**	.345**	.477**	.246**	–					
Practice Environment	Pearson Correlation	.789**	.263**	.137*	.741**	.400**	.463**	.693**	.379**	.607**	–				
Social Interferential Factor															

Dress Code	Pearson	-	-	-	-.670**	-.416**	-.489**	-.711**	-	-	-.675**	-				
	Correlation	.748**	.195**	.170**					.410**	.451**						
Gender Inequality	Pearson	-	-	-	-.634**	-.371**	-.409**	-.769**	-	-	-.609**	.703**	-			
	Correlation	.693**	.162**	.231**					.354**	.427**						
Sports Contribution of Female Athletes																
Health	Pearson	.788**	.251**	.151**	.696**	.389**	.545**	.752**	.365**	.515**	.736**	-	-.718**	-		
	Correlation											.781**				
Personal Drive	Pearson	.856**	.205**	.250**	.767**	.392**	.505**	.767**	.347**	.480**	.751**	-	-.773**	.702**	-	
	Correlation											.774**				
Interest	Pearson	.748**	.295**	.087	.704**	.407**	.454**	.843**	.336**	.468**	.676**	-	-.716**	.658**	.718**	-
	Correlation											.754**				

Noted. **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The results of predicting factors, outcome variable (sports contribution of female student athletes), and hypothesized model through path analysis were displayed in Figures 1 to 6.

Chi-Square = 36.389 df = 22 p = .028 cmin/df = 1.654
 CFI = .982 TLI = .970 RMSEA = .046

Figure 1. CFA of modified sports contribution model

Chi-Square = 209.669 df = 72 p = .000 cmin/df = 2.912
 CFI = .972 TLI = .955 RMSEA = .053

Figure 2. CFA of modified social support model

Chi-Square = 375.916 df = 145 p = .000 cmin/df = 2.592
 CFI = .987 TLI = .971 RMSEA = .049

Figure 3. CFA of modified social cultural model

Chi-Square = 119.255 df = 56 p = .000 cmin/df = 2.129
 CFI = .991 TLI = .982 RMSEA = .042

Figure 4. CFA of modified social personal model

Chi-Square = 93.647
CFI = .976

df = 43
TLI = .958

p = .000
RMSEA = .059

cmin/df = 2.177

Figure 5.CFA of modified social interferential model

The findings of hypothesized full path model in Table 3 indicated that the social support construct to sports contribution had a positive path coefficient (.58) with a highly significant *p-value*. Therefore, the other constructs as social cultural construct to sports contribution (.37) and social personal construct to sports contribution (.18) were found highly significant ($p < .001$).

Therefore, the effect of moderator construct (social interferential) in conjunction with social support construct to sports contribution was found at .75. Secondly, the effect of moderator construct (social interferential) in conjunction with social cultural construct to sports contribution was calculated at .28. Whereas, the effect of moderator construct (social interferential) in conjunction with social personal construct to sports contribution was counted at .62. All path coefficients were found highly significant with $p < 0.001$ according to the good-fit indices for path analysis (Table 3).

Figure 6.Hypothesized full path model

Table 3
Parameter estimates of hypothesized path model

			Path Coefficient (β)	C.R.	p-Value
Social Support	--->	SP	.58	19.982	***
Social Cultural	--->	SP	.37	13.056	***
Social Personal	--->	SP	.18	6.244	***
SSF X SIF	--->	SP	.75	15.648	***
SCF X SIF	--->	SP	.28	6.526	***
SPF X SIF	--->	SP	.62	14.707	***

Note: *** $p < 0.001$; C.R. = critical ratio.

*SC = Sports Contribution; *SSF = Social Support Factor; *SCF = Social Cultural Factor; *SPF = Social Personal Factor; *SIF = Social Interferential Factor.

Table 4
Covariance of hypothesized path model

			Covariance	C.R.	p-value
Social Support	<-->	Social Cultural	.624	9.356	***
Social Support	<-->	Social Personal	.616	9.265	***
Social Personal	<-->	Social Cultural	.596	9.045	***
SSF x SIF	<-->	SCF x SIF	.859	11.513	***
SSF x SIF	<-->	SPF x SIF	.859	11.513	***
SPF x SIF	<-->	SCF x SIF	.814	11.152	***

Note: *** $p < 0.001$; C.R. = critical ratio.

*SSF x *SIF = Social Support Factor x Social Interferential Factor; *SCF x *SIF = Social Cultural Factor x Social Interferential Factor; *SPF x *SIF = Social Personal Factor x Social Interferential Factor

The findings of covariance in Table 4 described that social support factor and social cultural factor both had a positive path coefficient (.62) with a highly significant level at $p < 0.001$. The findings also highlighted that social cultural factor and social personal factor had also found highly significant $p < 0.001$ with a positive path coefficient (.60). Thirdly, results showed that social support factor and social personal factor had a positive path coefficient (.62) with a highly significant level $p < 0.001$.

Therefore, as a moderator (social interferential) was found highly significant ($p < .001$) and when used in conjunction with predictors such as SSF x SIF (social support factor x social interferential factor) with SCF x SIF (social cultural factor x social interferential factor) existed strong relationship at $r = .86$. Likewise, the relationship existed at $r = .81$ between SCF x SIF (social cultural factor x social interferential factor) and SPF x SIF (social personal factor x social interferential factor). Lastly, SSF x SIF (social support factor x social interferential factor) with SPF x SIF (social personal factor x social interferential factor) existed a strong relationship at $r = .86$ (Table 4).

However, the path model proved that all path coefficients and covariance are found at their highly significant level ($p < 0.001$).

Discussion

The findings of [Cox, Dunccheon, and McDavid \(2009\)](#) indicated that students' associations with teachers and peers in sports may perform a critical part in supporting approaches of affiliation and, indirectly self-determined motivation. Consequently, female schools/institutions should work for payable consideration of the contribution of the sports of athletes and reflect in a broad sense through emerging approaches for the female athletes. Female athletes' feedback may also be absorbed for the improvements in sports contribution as well as in other emerging approaches. [Gairns, Whipp, and Jackson \(2015\)](#) expressed that when teachers were supposed to involve in performances they were thought of as attentive, supportive, and believing however, students would utilize these indications to understand that their teachers were extremely confident in their capabilities.

It has been observed that the social support provided by parents, siblings, peers, and sports teachers is too much spirited in generating female athletes and made their girls be able to participate in sports anywhere but the margin of mistakes is not of exception. Therefore, social support from parents, siblings, peers, and sports teachers is more needed to enhance the contribution of the sports through their appreciation, encouragement, love, support, and involvement provided to their female athletes. [Dawson and Downward \(2009\)](#) concluded that females with having their active family members promote their sports contribution. [Smith \(2003\)](#) investigated that in the competitive sports setting, in particular circumstances, an athlete may be distressed to give away competitive sport by her parents, however, sports teachers are encouraging her to continue. Furthermore, the

literature suggests that coaches, teachers, parents, and peers are those who form youth sports involvements, on the other hand, many types of research might deliver a well understanding of social impact have until now to be explored.

[Wentzel's \(1998\)](#) research on elementary and middle school students has revealed important relationships of students' insights of support and love from their parents, teachers, and peers. Alternatively, the researcher perceived through education institution management discussion during the data collection that every female athlete had been broadly supported to take part in sports with adequate sport training sessions before going to any sporting event. The management pointed out too that all female athletes are encouraged to participate in sports.

The sports training campus is frequently organized to encourage and develop the sports contribution and parents of entire girls are also invited to encourage their girls in sports contribution to appreciate them on their sports performance as well. This type of practice is encouraged to female athletes provided by the parents and educational institutions in their sports contribution as well as their sports performance. Although, the significance of sports contribution and its benefits such as promotion of health, improvement of self-confidence through the personal drive, and development of interest in sports all associated with the social support of female athletes' parents, siblings, peers, and sports teachers that may differ from person to person. Social support of parents, siblings, peers, and sports teachers is considered a leading, spirited, and valuable part of the sports' contribution of females.

Though, the findings revealed that the influence of the social cultural factor found most on health and interest of female athletes on sports contribution. However, the social cultural factor was not an impressive influence on the personal drive of female athletes' sports contributions. On the other hand, [Houlfort, Koestner, Joussemet, Nantel-Vivier, and Leke \(2002\)](#) exposed that performance-based rewards have a positive influence on female sports contribution. [Amorose and Horn \(2001\)](#) study confirmed that the awarding of scholarships in sports may have improved the athletes' insights of competency and consistently assisted intrinsic motivation. The study confirmed the significance of findings and found that social cultural construct had a great impact on female athletes' sports contribution overall. Particularly, if social culture fully encourages their female athletes within the community and educational institutions, this positively heartens the female athletes and makes them be more inciting in developing their sports contribution and performance as well. Educational institutions with sports teachers' consultancy should develop frequently the sports' contribution of female athletes as well as enhance participation opportunities in sports for all school girls.

The finding of the existing study revealed that the influence of social personal construct found significant on the sports' contribution of female student athletes. [Prichard and Tiggemann \(2008\)](#) investigated that in particular exercising to lose weight, to increase body tone, and to develop attractiveness have appeared such the mechanism in which females may develop more their physical personalities with more exercise, despite the related health and fitness benefits. Several former studies support the finding of the existing study, for example, [Kim's \(2013\)](#) sports participants reported considerably better body awareness, approachability, body satisfaction, and less self-objectification that social personal construct is much possible to affect sports contribution of female athletes. Therefore, school female athletes of Pakistan often lacking to find their suitable body physique or image. Comprehensive planning is needed by school management and sports teachers to provide opportunities and facilities where female athletes may develop their muscular physique to get the benefits towards improving their health and give a good look through their body physique and develop their beauty. This approach will not only enhance the sports' contribution of females but also boost the personal drive and interest of school girls towards sports and further successes.

Grounded on the entire finding, the results indicated that body image had a significant affiliation with the sub-variables of female athletes, however, the association was found medium but positive. Though, the body image application not only enhances the body posture but also helps to improve the health of female athletes. This approach may be developing the contribution of females in sports. However, this may be the reason for the weaker physique of female athletes that the facilities for the development of their bodies are less available than the male athletes. Cote (1999) expressed that in sports where peak performance is often achieved however, early specialization by adolescent females is often needed to achieve the best performance. [Ford, Yates, and Williams \(2010\)](#) it is essential that the practice is simulated in the training environment so that athletes are delivered with the opportunity to improve the awareness, intellectual, and motor skills required to perform in competition.

Sports contribution cannot be improved without providing equal resources to female athletes. Prior studies proved the results of current research ([Sani, Eskandarnejad, & Fathirezaie, 2016](#); [Coughlan, Williams, McRobert, & Ford, 2014](#); [Aghdam, Moghaddam, Jafarabadi, Allahverdipour, Nikookheslat, & Nourizadeh, 2013](#); [Duran & Agundez, 2013](#); [MacDonald, Cote, Eys, & Deakin, 2011](#); [Savage, DiNallo, & Downs, 2009](#); [Prichard & Tiggemann, 2008](#); [Aubrey, 2006](#); [Javed, 2014](#); [Burch, Clavio, Eagleman, Major, Pedersen, Frederick, & Blaszk, 2014](#); [Gurock, 2014](#); [McKay, 2013](#); [Helfert & Warschburger, 2013](#); [Impett, Henson, Breines, Schooler, & Tolman, 2011](#); [Szymanski, Moffitt, & Carr, 2011](#); [Berberick, 2010](#); [Jones, 2010](#); [Harbour, Behrens, Kim, & Kitchens, 2008](#)).

Conclusion and Implications

Descriptive analyses demonstrate the significant findings that Pakistani secondary schools/institutions are in the developing process of the sports facilities to female athletes which are needed to their sports contribution. The incentives (rewards) provided by the authorities/institutions are also not up to satisfactory perception by Pakistani female athletes. The current study found that the social interferential factor was fully moderated the relationship in conjunction with social support, social cultural, social personal individually, and the female athletes' sports contribution. Positive relationships were revealed between all constructs and the sports' contribution of female athletes.

It was concluded that there is the need to increase the sports facilities in female secondary schools in rural areas of Pakistan. Therefore, the school management may encourage the contribution of girls in sports. It was also needed for the provision of equal opportunities to female athletes comparatively provided to male athletes in Pakistan. The female sports organizations and associations are needed to raise the issue to higher authorities on this gender disparity and demand for equal rights of sports contribution opportunities for females. This may be done through facilitating sufficient financial support and awarding monthly scholarships, equal facilities and opportunities in sports, accessible approach to sports contribution in all competitions to female athletes because there is no discrimination existed in this global world of sports about the sports' contribution.

Furthermore, there is a lack of awareness about female sports participation in most of the Pakistani community. However, there is a need to develop the awareness of the whole community including parents about the benefits for their females through contribution in sports that their female athletes may develop their health and intellectual level. The need for seminars, community walks, public gatherings, and recreational events for females has still existed that could be fortified to promote female sports contribution and highlight the importance of female sports competencies in the future.

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